

Social Networking Sites (SNS) and Academic Performance Among High School Students in Bazar veng, Lunglei

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Abstract: *This study aims to explore the patterns of Social Networking Sites (SNS) among high school students and its implications on their academic performances. The study was descriptive in design and stratified proportionate sampling was used to identify the respondents. The sample size consisted of 60 samples including 20 students from class 9 of each school, which represent the overall population of the schools. The patterns of Social Networking Sites (SNS), academic performances and their relationship are measured. The results of the study indicates that there are gender differences in study habits and study patterns among the respondents. Moreover, the screen time on social networking sites does not have any negative impact upon the academic performances of the high school students in Bazar Veng community. However, proper care must be given to co-curricular activities in schools to engage and discover students hidden talents and resources.*

Keywords: *Social Networking Sites (SNS), academic performance, adolescents*

Introduction

A social networking site is an online platform that allows people to create profiles, connect with others, and share content such as text posts, photos, videos, and links within a virtual community. These platforms enable users to interact with friends, family, colleagues, or even strangers, forming social connections and networks.

Understanding these patterns helps social media platforms, marketers, and researchers analyse user behaviour, tailor content, and improve user experience on these sites. Patterns also provide insights into the social dynamics and trends that shape the online interactions of users within these digital communities.

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The main actors i.e. the adolescents or youth are facing the dilemma in trying to cope a life of both their academic performance and the tempting features and nature of social networking sites (SNS). This has become a social phenomenon surrounding the life of the adolescent and youth. Managing study hours and screen time has become a big challenge for them.

Overview of Literature

The digital technologies and social networking sites have negative impact on students' studying and habits. (Gok, T, 2016). Social Networking Sites (SNS) addiction is significantly and positively related to depression and neuroticism. Further, addiction to SNS negatively impacts their well-being, social and academic life of the students. (AlBarashdi, H. S., 2020).

In Mizoram context, the study by Lalnunpuii, E & Ngurtinkhuma (2021) reveals that among the respondents all the students were aware with SNSs and most of the students were having more than one account. Facebook, YouTube, Instagram was found the most commonly used SNSs. The main problems faced by the students while using SNSs are lack of privacy, poor internet facility, internet fraud and lack of technical knowledge.

Meanwhile, Buragohain, P & Devi, K (2018) highlighted in their work that students used WhatsApp most and they used SNS through their smart phone for both academic as well as for entertainment purposes. Social Networking Sites had both positive and negative impacts on student community.

Another study by Abdalla, R., & Qashou, A. (2020) also concluded that only student faculty and computer self-efficacy significantly influences SNS use, which in turn positively and significantly influence the academic performance. This indicates the better the knowledge of social networking sites usages, the more productive they are for academic performances.

Kaur, N & Rai, M (2023) in their research reveals that students gained more knowledge and information regarding study through internet or social media. At the same time, social networking sites have negative impact on the academic performance of students due to the fact that they excessively used them for entertainment purpose and has raised the level of anxiety, stress and depression.

Social Networking Sites (SNS) usage promotes academic performances and even strengthens student-teacher relationship through the online platform which positively enhance teaching-learning experiences. (A AIOqlah, R.M, 2023).

Batra, N & Goswami, R (2019) discussed how social media has contributed to an increase in cybercrime among college students. It has become a status symbol for students, as well as a place where they may express a different aspect of their personality while concealing the reality. Excessive consumption has a negative impact on their health and academic performance, leading to cybercrime due to jealousy, dissatisfaction, peer pressure, and other factors. As a result, parents and teachers must address this issue and educate students about the risks linked with the Internet, as well as the laws that protect them.

Statement of the problem

Although the social media has various advantages, its usage adversely affected academic performance when the networking sites were used for the purpose of non-academic purposes. If the use of internet is not controlled properly it can have negative impact so this is study in order to know if the usage of social networking sites among high school students in Bazarveng, Lunglei have negative or positive impact.

In the academic world, everyone views social networking sites as a distraction and leads to negative impact on student academic performances in a negative way but some also claims that social networking sites helps them in their academic related. Studies found that students who spend more time on social media sites are likely to demonstrate poor academic performance. This is because they spend time chatting online and making friends on social media sites instead of reading books.

The study aims to address this phenomenon by understanding the pattern of Social Networking Sites (SNS) usage, academic related concerns of the adolescents and examining the relationship between screen time and academic performance

Methodology

Research design

This study is descriptive in design and followed mixed methods of data in nature. The influence of social media usage on the academic performance, along with the patterns of their social networking site usage are analyze in this study.

Sampling

For the purpose of this study, stratified proportionate sampling technique was employed in identifying the respondents for the study. The study was conducted in three high schools in Bazar veng community, Lunglei

namely Solomons Higher Secondary School, Govt. Bazar High School and Adventist English School (AEC) respectively. Adolescents that are attending schooling in high school represent the universe of the study. This study is descriptive in design and followed mixed methods of data in nature.

The sample size consisted of 60 samples including 20 students from class 9 of each school, which represent the overall population of the schools.

Thus, the overall sample size comprised of 60 students, with 27 male and 33 female students selected from the three schools.

Tools of data collection

Semi Structured Questionnaire was used for collection of data. The questionnaire is divided into 3 sections. The sections are profile of the respondent, pattern of social networking sites usage and academic related concerns.

Results and discussions

This section deals with the results and discussions of the study. They are structured into seven parts. They are profile of the respondents, patterns of using Social Networking Sites (SNS), parental restrictions, academic concerns, pattern of learning, nature of learning and inter-correlation matrix.

Profile of the respondents

The demographic profile of the respondents was classified into age group, types of device use, brand of the device and price of the device.

The study shows that more than two-thirds (71.9%) of the respondents are aged between 15 and 17 years. 96.9 percent use mobile devices to access the internet. A little more than one third (35.0%) of the respondents use the Redmi brand to access SNS. Concerning the price of the device, two-fifths (40.0%) of the respondents use a device with a price range between ₹10,000/ - ₹15,000/- rupees.

Table 01: Profile of the respondents

S/N	Variables	Gender		Total
		Male	Female	N=60
		n=27	n=33	
I Age Group				
	12-14	9 (28.1)	18 (64.3)	27 (45)
	15-17	23 (71.9)	10 (35.7)	33 (55)
II Types of device use				
	Phone	32 (100)	26 (92.9)	58 (96.7)
	PC (Desktop)	0 (0)	1 (3.6)	1 (1.7)
	Laptop	0 (0)	1 (3.6)	1 (1.7)
III Brand of the device				
	Redmi	12 (37.5)	9 (32.1)	21 (35)
	Oppo	7 (21.9)	3 (10.7)	10 (16.7)
	i Phone	0 (0)	2 (7.1)	2 (3.3)
	Poco	1 (3.1)	1 (3.6)	2 (3.3)
	Vivo	2 (6.3)	7 (25)	9 (15)
	Realme	4 (12.5)	2 (7.1)	6 (10)
	Samsung	2 (6.3)	3 (10.7)	5 (8.3)
	Others	4 (2.5)	1 (3.6)	5 (8.3)
IV Price of the device (in rupees)				
	Below ₹5000	0 (0)	2 (7.1)	2 (3.3)
	₹5000-10000	11 (34.4)	7 (25)	18 (30)
	₹10000-15000	9 (28.1)	15 (53.6)	24 (40)
	₹15000-20000	12 (37.5)	2 (7.1)	14 (23.3)
	₹20000-30000	0 (0)	1 (3.6)	1 (1.7)
	₹30000 Above	0 (0)	1 (3.6)	1 (1.7)

Source: Computed Figures in parenthesis are percentages

Patterns of accessing Social Networking Sites (SNS)

Table 2 shows the patterns of accessing social networking sites (SNS) which are classified into motives, favourites sites and screen time.

Based on the findings, 25 percent of the respondents utilize social networking sites for communication, as well as for knowledge and creativity. Additionally, 41.7% of respondents named Instagram as their favorite social networking site, primarily due to the tempting features to watch reels. The average screen time on a continues basis is between 1-2 hours per day.

Table 02 Motives of Social Networking Sites (SNS)

S/N	Variables	Gender		Total N=60
		Male n=27	Female n=33	
I	Motive of using SNS			
	Entertainment	10 (31.3)	3 (10.7)	13 (21.7)
	Communication	5 (15.6)	10 (35.7)	15 (25.0)
	Time Pass	1 (3.1)	8 (28.6)	9 (15.0)
	Academic related	5 (15.6)	1 (3.6)	6 (10.0)
	Keeping in pace with others	1 (3.1)	0 (0.0)	1 (1.7)
	Knowledge and creativity	9 (28.1)	6 (21.4)	15 (25.0)
	Others	1 (3.1)	0 (0.0)	1 (1.7)
II	Favorite social networking sites			
	YouTube	16 (50.0)	6 (21.4)	22 (36.7)
	WhatsApp	6 (18.8)	4 (14.3)	10 (16.7)
	Facebook	2 (6.3)	0 (0.0)	2 (3.3)
	Instagram	7 (21.9)	18 (64.3)	25 (41.7)
	Google+	1 (3.1)	0 (0.0)	1 (1.7)
III	Average hours spend on social networking sites per day			
	Less Than 1 Hour	7 (21.9)	1 (3.6)	8 (13.3)
	1-2 Hours	14 (43.8)	9 (32.1)	23 (38.3)
	2-3hours	6 (18.8)	8 (28.6)	14 (23.3)
	3-4hours	2 (6.3)	7 (25.0)	9 (15.0)
	4-5hours	3 (9.4)	2 (7.1)	5 (8.3)
	More than 6 hours	0 (0.0)	1 (3.6)	1 (1.7)

Source: Computed Figures in parenthesis are percentages

Parental restrictions

The findings revealed that 68.3% of the respondents were restricted from using their devices by parents, and 98.3 percent were not allowed to take their devices to school.

Table 03. Parental restrictions

S/N	Variables	Gender		Total N=60
		Male n=27	Female n=33	
I	Restriction from parent on using your device			
	Yes	21 (65.6)	20 (71.4)	41 (68.3)
	No	11 (34.4)	8 (28.6)	19 (31.7)
II	Do you take your gadget to school?			
	Yes	0 (0.0)	1 (3.6)	1 (1.7)
	No	32 (100.0)	27 (96.4)	59 (98.3)

Source: Computed Figures in parenthesis are percentages

4.15 Academic concerns

Table 4 represents the academic concerns of the adolescents which are classified into academic performance, favourite study time, learning style and concentration hours on studies in a single span of time.

The study reveals that over half of the students (56.7%) had an average academic performance. About a fifth of the respondents (21.7%) had a high or low academic performance, with both percentages being equal.

According to the findings, around 21.7% of the respondent's study for 1-2 hours or 2-3 hours, which have an equivalent percentage. Also, a little less than 43.3% of the respondents prefer to study at night time. The majority (80%) of the respondents have their own study table. Additionally, around 86.7% of the respondents feel that the read/write learning style suits them the best. Lastly, less than one-third (36.7%) of the respondents can concentrate for less than 1 hour during their studies on a single span of time without any distractions or breaks.

Table 04 Academic concerns

S/N	Variables	Gender		Total
		Male	Female	N=60
		n=27	n=33	
I	Academic performance			
	Low	6 (10)	7 (11.7)	13 (21.7)
	Average	20 (33.3)	14 (23.30)	34 (56.7)
	High	6 (10)	7 (11.7)	13 (21.7)
II	Favorite study time			
	Early Morning	18 (56.3)	4 (14.3)	22 (36.7)
	Day Time	1 (3.1)	3 (10.7)	4 (6.7)
	Evening	1 (3.1)	3 (10.7)	4 (6.7)
	Night Time	11 (34.4)	15 (53.6)	26 (43.3)
	Late Night	1 (3.1)	3 (10.7)	4 (6.7)
III	Learning style			
	Visual	0 (0)	2 (7.1)	2 (3.3)
	Auditory	3 (9.4)	0 (0)	3 (5)
	Read/Write	29 (90.6)	23 (82.1)	52 (86.7)
	Kinesthetic	0 (0)	3 (10.7)	3 (5)
IV	Concentration hours on study			
	Less Than 1hour	5 (15.6)	17 (60.7)	22 (36.7)
	1-2 Hour	13 (40.6)	8 (28.6)	21 (35)
	2-3hours	7 (21.9)	3 (10.7)	10 (16.7)
	3-4hours	3 (9.4)	0 (0)	3 (5)
	More Than 5hours	4 (12.5)	0 (0)	4 (6.7)

Source: Computed Figures in parenthesis are percentages

Pattern of learning

Table 05 shows respondent pattern of learning by t-test distribution. The concerns regarding the pattern of learning of the respondents are categorized into daily, weekly, monthly, near or during class tests and near or during exams. Among the respondents mean scores, majority (2.07) pattern of learning is near or during class exam in which the majority (2.41) mean score are male respondents. Based on the mean score, the male youth study more near or during exam because they are usually neglecting their studies in a systematic manner or routine.

The T-test analysis reveals that there is a significance difference between male and female in studying near or during exams. The male youth study more near or during exam because they are usually neglecting their studies in a systematic manner or routine.

Table 05 Pattern of learning by gender

Pattern of learning	Male		Female		Total		t test	P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Daily	1.69	0.90	1.54	0.58	1.62	0.76	.768	.446
Weekly	2.25	0.51	2.43	0.63	2.33	0.57	-1.210	.231
Monthly	2.28	0.77	2.07	0.90	2.18	0.83	.972	.335
Near or during class test	1.72	1.05	1.68	1.09	1.70	1.06	.145	.885
Near or during exam	2.41	1.29	1.68	1.25	2.07	1.31	2.211	0.03*
Overall pattern of learning	2.07	0.47	1.88	0.56	1.98	0.52	1.432	.158

Source: Computed

*p<0.05

**p<0.01

Nature of learning

The concern regarding the nature of learning of the respondents are categorized into enjoy time spend on studies, love for learning, balanced time between academic and social networking sites usage, maintenance of class performance, meeting studies target, covering syllabus with little time devoted to studies and competing well in studies. Among the respondents mean scores, majority (2.12) nature of learning is competing well in studies which the majority (2.54) mean score are female respondent.

The T-test analysis shows that there is a significant relationship between male and female in regards to competing well in studies. The female are more competitive in their studies and outlook to life than their male counter-parts because they are more competitive and sincere their studies.

Table 06 Nature of learning by gender

Gender	Male		Female		Total		t Value	P Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Enjoy time spend on studies	1.94	0.80	2.46	0.88	2.18	0.87	-2.426	.018
Love for learning	2.25	1.02	2.32	0.94	2.28	0.98	-.281	.780
Balance time between studies and social networking usage	1.88	0.94	2.46	1.07	2.15	1.04	-2.268	.027
Maintenance of class Performance	1.59	0.50	2.07	0.72	1.82	0.65	-3.027	.004
Meeting studies target	2.09	0.69	2.21	0.92	2.15	0.80	-.580	.564
Covering syllabus with little Time devoted to studies	2.19	0.54	2.18	0.94	2.18	0.75	.046	.964
Competing well in studies	1.75	0.98	2.54	1.04	2.12	1.08	-3.011	.004**
Overall nature of learning	1.96	0.35	2.32	0.48	2.13	0.45	-3.386	.001

Source: Computed *p<0.05 **p<0.01

Inter-Correlation matrix of screen time on SNSs and Academic Performance

Table 07 shows Pearson’s Inter Correlation Matrix of gender, screen time on social networking sites and academic performances.

The correlation and coefficient between screen time on social networking sites and academic performance, the P value is .303* which indicate there is a moderate relationship between screen time on SNSs and academic performance.

This shows that there is a relationship between screen time on SNSs and gender whereas the screen time on SNSs does not affects academic performance of the respondent.

Table 07 Inter correlation matrix of screen time on SNSs and academic performance

Variables	Gender	Screen time on SNS	Academic Performance
Gender	1		
Screen time on SNS	.303*	1	
Academic Performance	0.000	-.060	1

Source: Computed **Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Conclusion

The study indicates that there are gender differences in study habits and study patterns among the respondents. Moreover, the screen time on social networking sites does not have any negative impact upon the academic performances of the high school students in Bazarveng community. However, proper care must be given to co-curricular activities in schools to engage and discover students hidden talents and resources. Also, learning habits need to be inculcated among the students in order to develop systematic studying and zeal for learning new ideas and knowledge which are essential for their growth in the present and future careers.

Implications of the study

The results of the study could be used to create awareness among adolescents in positive management of screen time and productive usage of social networking sites (SNS) in order to enhance new skills, knowledge building and integrate technology into academic excellence.

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